

THE POSTBUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF BLADE-STIFFENED

CARBON-EPOXY PANELS LOADED IN COMPRESSION

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Summary

An experimental study has been performed to investigate the post-buckling behaviour of blade-stiffened carbon-epoxy panels loaded in compression. The panel skin-laminates consisted of only a few layers due to the relatively low design loads, which implied that certain coupling terms in the stiffness matrices were thought to be no longer insignificant. Full scale panels and short columns with two different skin lay-ups have been tested. The full scale panels buckled in a global mode and did not show any postbuckling strength. The short columns, buckling in a local mode, supported approximately 1.8 times the initial buckling load before failure. Analytical results from a non-linear general shell finite element analysis show a good agreement with the test results; analytical results obtained from an efficient elastic buckling analysis computer code give good results only in case of the local buckling mode. The influence of the coupling terms on the buckling behaviour of the specimens is relatively small: it decreases the buckling load slightly, does not change the end shortening curves significantly and is mainly apparent in the out-of-plane deflections.

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Introduction

The introduction of composite materials in lightly loaded structures such as aircraft stabilizer panels implies the application of thin laminates, built up from a relatively small number of layers. When such laminates contain a number of $\pm 45^\circ$ layers with respect to the main load axis, coupling terms in the stiffness matrices may attain significant values. As these structural components are often designed to buckle at or even below the design ultimate loading condition, the effect of the coupling terms on the buckling and postbuckling behaviour must be well understood. Analysis of the postbuckling behaviour of compression-loaded classical unstiffened plates has resulted in analytical solutions for specially orthotropic plates (1, 2) and for general plates with coupling effects (3, 4). It has been established that these effects tend to reduce the buckling load of such plates and influence the axial and flexural stiffness. Publications on the postbuckling behaviour of stiffened panels loaded in compression are limited in number (5) and do not deal with coupling effects.

At the National Aerospace Laboratory (NLR) an experimental program has been carried out to study the buckling behaviour of blade-stiffened carbon-epoxy panels loaded in compression. The moderate load level for which these panels were designed has resulted in skin laminates with a thickness varying from a 7-ply 1.4 mm (representative for a root-section) to a 5-ply 1.0 mm (representative for a tip-section of a stabilizer). As the skin laminates consist of $\pm 45^\circ$ layers with 0° layers sandwiched in between, coupling terms in the stiffness matrices are no longer negligible and can be expected to have a noticeable effect on the buckling behaviour of the panels. Analytical results have been obtained with the BUCCLASP elastic buckling analysis computer code (6) and with the STAGS-C1 non-linear general shell analysis computer code (7) for comparison with typical test results and to calculate the effect of the coupling terms on the buckling behaviour of the panels.

Test Specimens

The specimens used in the experimental study were made by the Fokker Aircraft Company from unidirectional T300 carbon fibre tape preimpregnated with 120 °C (250 °F) cure Hexcel F155 thermosetting epoxy resin at a fibre volume content of 54 %. Specific lamina elastic properties of this material are presented in Table I.

Table I. Carbon-epoxy lamina properties

Longitudinal Young's modulus, GPa	115.0
Transverse Young's modulus, GPa	7.1
Shear modulus, GPa	4.0
Major Poisson's ratio	0.31
Nominal lamina thickness, mm	0.2

Six panels (length = 1100 mm, width = 330 mm, six blade stiffeners) were manufactured in two different configurations (3 panels each) representing a root-section and a tip-section of the stabilizer, featuring different skin-thicknesses. As the root-section panels were designed to have equal local and global buckling loads, they were not expected to have any postbuckling strength. In order to study the postbuckling behaviour of this

type of panel in a local buckling mode, one panel of each configuration was subdivided into short columns with specimen lengths selected to give initial buckling modes with four longitudinal half waves.

a) PANEL GEOMETRY AND ANALYTICAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

b) STIFFENER GEOMETRY DETAILS

Figure 2 - Typical test specimen

Figure 1 - Full scale panel geometry stiffener details and analytical boundary conditions. Dimensions are in millimetres

Figure 1 presents the full scale panel geometry and stiffener details, while Figure 2 shows a typical test specimen. Stacking sequences for skins and stiffeners are given in Table II, and stiffness matrices for these panel elements are presented in Table III. The coupling terms of the stiffness matrices are evident. They are determined by the fabrication technique used to build these integrally stiffened, cocured panels. A view of the panel lay-up procedure is given in Figure 3 which illustrates how torsion-extensional coupling terms B16 and B26, introduced by nonsymmetrical lay-ups cannot be avoided. This is caused by the fact that the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies run from one stiffener via the skin into the next stiffener, where the ply-angle changes sign. In order to keep the stiffener lay-up symmetrical, every other skin lay-up between stiffeners inevitably turns out to be non-symmetrical. The bending-torsional coupling terms D16 and D26 in symmetrical skin elements (and stiffeners) result from the larger contribution to the bending stiffness of the outermost $+45^\circ$ layers compared to that of the adjacent -45° layers or vice versa. These terms become of importance in case of thin laminates such as the symmetrical skin elements of the panels. Full scale panels were subdivided into short columns with either three or six stiffeners. The root-section panel was divided into two specimens of each configuration; of the tip section panel

Table II. Skin and stiffener laminates

Design	Symmetrical Skin (S)	Non-symmetrical Skin (NS)	Stiffener type a	Stiffener type b
root	$(\bar{+}45/0_3/\pm 45)$	$(\pm 45/0_3/\pm 45)$	$(\pm 45/0_6/\bar{+}45)$	$(\bar{-}45/0_6/\pm 45)$
tip	$(\bar{+}45/0/\pm 45)$	$(\pm 45/0/\pm 45)$	$(\pm 45/0_6/\bar{+}45)$	$(\bar{-}45/0_6/\pm 45)$

Figure 3 - Panel lay-up procedure (root-section)

Table III. Laminate stiffness matrices

Design	Element	Stiffness matrices A, B, D					
Root/tip	stiffener type a (b)	167474	24908	0	0	0	0
			37222	0	0	0	0
				28480	0	0	0
					35378	14856	(-)3473
					19747	(-)3473	16047
Root	Symmetrical skin	98063	23580	0	0	0	0
			32936	0	0	0	0
				26080	0	0	0
					9627	5899	-2171
					7673	-2171	6308
Root	Non-symmetri- cal skin	98063	23580	0	0	0	-2171
			32936	0	0	0	-2171
				26080	-2171	-2171	0
					9627	5899	0
					7673	0	6308
Tip	Symmetrical skin	51788	22694	0	0	0	0
			30080	0	0	0	0
				24880	0	0	0
					3038	2301	-1303
					2965	-1303	2450
Tip	Non-symmetri- cal skin	51788	22694	0	0	0	-2171
			30080	0	0	0	-2171
				24880	-2171	-2171	0
					3038	2301	0
					2965	0	2450

only two 3-stiffener specimens were made. Short column geometry is presented in Figure 4.

All specimens were cured in an autoclave. Ultrasonic inspection did not reveal any detectable defects. To ensure uniform compressive loading and to avoid brooming of the carbon fibres during testing, the loaded ends of the specimens were potted in an epoxy-resin material and subsequently machined flat and parallel. The out-of-plane displacements of the panels were made visible by means of the Moiré-shadow technique for which reason the unstiffened sides of the specimens were painted white. Stiffener tops were painted white as well, to facilitate the observation of the buckling deflections.

Figure 4 - Short column geometry

Apparatus and Tests

Tests were performed using a 900 kN-capacity servo-hydraulic testing machine (Wolpert-Amsler), which was equipped with box-beams to introduce the compressive load. The unloaded panel edges were unsupported. Loading of the specimens took place under displacement control in steps of .02 mm or .04 mm. Strains were recorded with pairs of strain gauges applied back-to-back, and linear variable differential transformers were used to record out-of-plane and longitudinal in-plane displacements at selected locations, recording taking place at each load step. At some load steps out-of-plane displacements were visualized with sliding transducers passing over the panel surface, and with the Moiré-shadow technique. For this purpose a 1 line per mm grid has been used, covering approximately one half of a full scale panel.

Originally it was planned to load the full size panels to failure but at the time when increasing end-shortening resulted in just a rapid increase of the transverse deflections without adding any load to the specimens, the tests were stopped to save the panels for future experiments. The short columns, however, were all loaded to failure, which occurred at still increasing loads.

Analysis

In this study analytical results have been obtained with the BUCLASP and STAGS computer codes. To predict the initial buckling response of the specimens, calculations have been performed with the elastic buckling analysis computer code BUCLASP (6). In this program effects of pre-buckling deformations and initial imperfections are ignored. Simply supported conditions without restrictions on the axial warping displacements u are assumed along the loaded edges. The prismatic structure is assumed to buckle into an integer number of half-waves in the longitudinal (x) direction, the number being the same in all elements, skin or stiffener. For each lamina the stress-strain equations used in the analysis assume orthotropy with respect to the axes of the stiffened plate. This implies that laminate stiffness elements A16, A26, B16, B26, D16 and D26 do not appear in the analysis, that is, the influence of coupling effects on the buckling load is ignored.

The BUCLASP model for the full scale panels is shown in Figure 5a. The stiffness represented by the unidirectional filler material at the skin-stiffener intersection is accounted for by the addition of beams. Three different buckling modes have been found, shown in Figure 5b.

* h = SKIN LAMINATE THICKNESS

a) BUCLASP-MODEL (WITH BEAMS TO REPRESENT FILLER)

b) BUCLASP SOLUTIONS

Figure 5 - Full scale panel analysis with BUCLASP, model and buckling modes

Table IV. BUCLASP analysis on full scale panels

Design	Buckling mode	Half wave-length (mm)	Buckling load (kN)	End-shortening at buckling (mm)
root	Euler	530	101	2.142
	Local	71	104	2.204
tip	Local	56	73	2.212
	Torsional	530	81	2.446
	Euler	530	81	2.454

Table V. BUCLASP analysis on short columns

Design	Number of stiffeners	Half wave-length (mm)	Buckling load (kN)	End-shortening at buckling (mm)
root	6	76	104	.682
root	3	76	50	.708
tip	3	49	36	.681

Table IV presents the results of this analysis, which confirms the coinciding global and local modes for the root-section panel, while the tip-section panel is calculated to buckle clearly in a local mode, with coinciding torsional and global modes at a higher load level. A similar model has been used for the short column analysis resulting in local buckling modes as shown in Figure 6 and buckling loads as given in Table V.

a) ROOT SECTION, 6 STIFFENER TYPE

b) ROOT SECTION, 3 STIFFENER TYPE

c) TIP SECTION, 3 STIFFENER TYPE

Figure 6 - Short column analysis with BUCLASP, buckling modes

Figure 7 - STAGS analysis model

The postbuckling response of the specimens has been analysed with the STAGS model shown in Figure 7. The finite elements used are combined membrane and bending quadrilateral elements with midside nodes (type 411). As shown in Figure 7 the finite element model has 4 plate elements across the skin between stiffeners, the stiffeners were modelled by 1 plate element and the unidirectional filler material was again modelled by discrete beams.

The short columns have 25 elements in the longitudinal direction, about six per half wave length. To limit the number of degrees of freedom, only one half of the full scale panels was modelled, with 25 elements in the longitudinal direction and symmetrical boundary conditions were applied (see Figure 1). Due to the coupling terms in the laminate stiffness matrices, conditions of symmetry do not exist,

but for full scale panels buckling in a global mode this inaccuracy was thought to be acceptable. As these coupling terms change from one inter-stiffener skin element to the next their effect was assumed to be more severe on the local buckling response of the short columns.

The loading and boundary conditions applied in the analysis were selected to be in accordance with the actual test conditions. The loading was introduced by the application of a uniform end-shortening to one end of the specimen; the boundary conditions are shown in figure 1a. Initial geometric imperfections were based on the initial buckling modes, with amplitudes of .2 mm in case of the full scale panels and of .01 mm in case of the short columns.

Results and Discussion

Full Scale Panels

Each full scale panel tested in this investigation showed noticeable prebuckling out-of-plane deformations, caused by bending of the panels both in the longitudinal and lateral direction, resulting in a hollowness when observed from the skin side. Subsequently the panels buckled in a global mode, where small additions to the end shortening resulted in rapidly increasing transverse deflections without adding any load to the specimens. When the transverse deflections attained large values, the development of a local buckling pattern could be observed at the center of the panels. The tests were stopped before failure occurred, to save the panels for future experiments. Table VI presents the experimentally determined buckling load, corresponding end-shortening and maximum load for each panel, as well as the analytically determined results obtained with and without taking account of the influence of the coupling terms.

Table VI. Results for full scale panels

Specimen Design	<u>Experimental results</u>			<u>Analytical results (STAGS)</u>			
	Buckling load (kN)	Maximum load (kN)	End shortening at buckling (mm)	<u>with coupling terms</u>		<u>without coupling terms</u>	
				Buckling load (kN)	End shortening at buckling (mm)	Buckling load (kN)	End shortening at buckling (mm)
FBP 21 root	87	88	1.86	89	1.86	91	1.91
FBP 22 root	87	88	1.80				
FBP 31 tip	62	63	1.88	62	1.82	66	1.94
FBP 32 tip	65	66	1.91				

The initial buckling load was identified by plotting the squared values of the bending strains, obtained from the strain gauge recordings and out-of-plane displacements, obtained from the linear variable differential transformers versus the load. Prebuckling out-of-plane deflections, and the development of local buckling patterns well in the postbuckling region were visualized by means of the Moiré shadow technique. Typical Moiré-fringe patterns for specimen FBP 31 in the prebuckling region at an applied load equal to 30 kN, and in the postbuckling region at an applied load equal to 62 kN are shown in Figure 8.

a) SPECIMEN AT AN APPLIED LOAD OF 30 kN

b) SPECIMEN AT AN APPLIED LOAD OF 62 kN

Figure 8 - Buckling pattern of full scale panel FBP31, tip section

Comparison between test results and analytical results obtained with the STAGS computer code presented in Table VI reveals that the buckling load is well predicted; slightly higher buckling loads are obtained with calculations disregarding the influence of the coupling terms. Figures 9a and 10a give end shortening results for both panels as a function of the applied compressive load; apparently the axial stiffness of the root-section panel has been slightly overestimated.

Figures 9b and 10b compare the out-of-plane deflections at the center of the panel for both types of analysis, which shows that only in case of the tip-section panel the influence of the coupling terms leads to a decrease of the additional load carrying capacity in the postbuckling region. The out-of-plane deflection measured near the middle of the specimens is compared with analytical results in figures 9c and 10c. A fair correlation is found; the initial geometric imperfections of the specimens are suspected to cause small differences, especially at lower values of the deflections.

Several views of (one half of) the deflected panels, generated with the STAGS computer code are shown in Figures 9d-f and 10d-f. For a root-section panel the development of a local buckling pattern in the postbuckling region at a maximum panel deflection larger than 6 mm is illustrated in Figures 9d and 9c. Figure 9f shows that the analysis in which the coupling terms were not taken into account does not produce this buckling pattern, at least not up to a maximum panel deflection of 7.5 mm. Figure 10d shows a deflected tip-section panel at a maximum panel deflection of 7.25 mm, featuring a well developed local buckling pattern at the center of the panel. Another area of local buckling is found near the loaded ends, which in fact was developed in the prebuckling region as a result of in-plane restraints imposed by the flat end test conditions. The same phenomenon was found by the analysis without coupling terms (Figure 10e).

a) END SHORTENING

d) DEFLECTED PANEL

b) OUT-OF-PLANE DEFLECTION

e) DEFLECTED PANEL

c) OUT-OF-PLANE DEFLECTION

f) DEFLECTED PANEL

Figure 9 - Full scale panel test results; root section

a) END SHORTENING

d) DEFLECTED PANEL

b) OUT-OF-PLANE DEFLECTION

e) DEFLECTED PANEL

c) OUT-OF-PLANE DEFLECTION

f) DEFLECTED PANEL

Figure 10 - Full scale panel results; tip section

In this case a local buckling pattern in the center of the panel started to develop at a maximum panel deflection of 5.5 mm (Figure 10f) as opposed to 2 mm for the analysis with coupling terms. The out-of-plane behaviour as predicted by the STAGS analysis correlates well with Moiré-fringe patterns as shown in Figure 8.

The prebuckling out-of-plane deformation of the panels, i.e. the increased hollowness of the panel skins was also well predicted, by both types of analysis, which leads to the conclusion that this behaviour is caused by the combination of the initial geometric imperfection, corresponding approximately with the first global buckling mode, and the boundary conditions at the loaded ends. It is this prebuckling out-of-plane behaviour of the panels which is suspected to produce such a large overestimation of the buckling load by the BUCLASP analysis of about 15 %; neglectation of the coupling terms has only a minor influence.

Short Columns

The short columns tested in this configuration buckled into a local buckling mode, in which both the stiffeners and the skin deformed, at an applied load close to the analytically predicted buckling load. Each specimen failed at an applied load approximately 80 % greater than the experimentally determined buckling load. Table VII presents the experimentally determined buckling load, corresponding end shortening and failure load for each specimen, as well as some analytically determined results, obtained with and without taking account of the influence of the coupling terms.

Table VII. Results for short columns

Specimen Design	<u>Experimental results</u>			<u>Analytical results (STAGS)</u>			
	Buckling load (kN)	Failure load (kN)	End shortening at buckling (mm)	<u>with coupling terms</u>		<u>without coupling terms</u>	
				Buckling load (kN)	End shortening at buckling (mm)	Buckling load (kN)	End shortening at buckling (mm)
FBS 23 root-6st.	100	181	.70	102	.64	105	.66
FBS 24 root-6st.	100	194	.70				
FBS 21 root-3st.	52	95	.80				
FBS 22 root-3st.	51	88	.78				
FBS 31 tip-3st.	38	75	.75				
FBS 32 tip-3st.	40	72	.76				

The initial buckling load was identified from the end shortening plot. The identification of the buckling load from bending strain and out-of-plane displacement plots was hampered by the uneven development of the buckling pattern, leading to a large scatter. The buckling mode of each specimen, and the development of the out-of-plane deflection patterns corresponding with the postbuckling response of the panel skins were visualized with the Moiré shadow technique. The buckling mode of each specimen had one lateral halfwave in each skin element between stiffeners and four longitudinal halfwaves. Typical Moiré-fringe patterns for specimen FBS 23 with an applied load equal to the buckling load of 100 kN, and with an applied load equal to 170 kN just before failure are shown in Figure 11.

a) SPECIMEN AT AN APPLIED LOAD OF 100 kN

b) SPECIMEN AT AN APPLIED LOAD OF 170 kN

Figure 11 - Buckling pattern of short column FBS23, root section

Figure 12a shows the end shortening results of the root-section short columns with 6 stiffeners as a function of the applied compressive load. Analytical buckling solutions by STAGS, with and without the influence of the coupling terms are also presented, as well as the BUCLASP solution which is represented by the open circle. The axial stiffness of this root-section is overestimated mainly because of small differences with the actual specimen geometry. Apart from this deviation of the prebuckling stiffness a good correlation is found, both with the STAGS results and with the BUCLASP results. The influence of the coupling terms is only minor with respect to the end shortening behaviour. The out-of-plane deflections measured near the middle of one of the specimens are compared with analytical results in Figure 12b. Differences between the three curves are caused by the fact that the buckling patterns consist of relatively short waves and have nodal lines which do not coincide exactly. The STAGS results are also influenced by the initial geometric imperfection represented by the lowest buckling mode with a .01 mm amplitude which is not representative for the actual specimens. Figures 12c-f present several views of the deflected panels, generated with the STAGS computer code. Comparison of Figure 12e with Figure 12f shows the influence of the bending-torsional coupling terms, which resulted in skewed buckles. This was also found in the experiments, as shown in Figure 11b, where the second and fourth inter-stiffener skin bays show skewed buckles. Failure of all short column specimens probably initiated at the free stiffener ends, and resulted in a complete fracture of the cross-section along a nodal line.

a) END SHORTENING

b) OUT-OF-PLANE DEFLECTION

c) DEFLECTED PANEL

d) DEFLECTED PANEL

e) DEFLECTED STIFFENERS

f) DEFLECTED STIFFENERS

Figure 12- Short column results; root section

Concluding Remarks

The postbuckling behaviour of blade-stiffened carbon-epoxy panels loaded in compression has been investigated, both experimentally and analytically. Full scale panels buckling in a global mode as well as short columns buckling in a local mode were tested in this investigation. As these panels were designed for relatively low compressive loads the skin laminates consisted of just a few layers, implying that certain coupling terms in the stiffness matrices were not insignificant.

The full scale panels buckled in a global mode and did not show any additional load carrying capacity in the postbuckled state; the short columns buckled in a local buckling mode and supported about 1.8 times their initial buckling loads before failing. The full scale panels were not tested to failure; failure of the short columns probably initiated at the free stiffener ends and resulted in a complete fracture of the cross-section along a nodal line.

Analytical results obtained with the BUCLASP elastic buckling analysis computer code and with the STAGS non-linear general shell analysis computer code were compared with the experimental results. The results obtained with STAGS showed a good agreement. BUCLASP results gave a 15 % overestimation of the global buckling loads, mainly because of the inability to take into account the prebuckling out-of-plane behaviour of the panels. In case of the local buckling loads a good agreement of the BUCLASP results with the experimental results was found.

The influence of the coupling terms on the buckling behaviour of the specimens was limited: it reduced the buckling loads slightly and did not change the end shortening curves significantly. Its main effect was on the out-of-plane deflections. Short columns buckling in a local buckling mode showed skewed buckles because of the bending torsional coupling terms and the development of a local buckling pattern in the middle of the full scale panels, already buckled in a global mode was promoted.

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